

Lateral Canals - Terminologies, Classification and Prevalence in Permanent and Deciduous Teeth: A Comprehensive Review

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ABSTRACT

A clear understanding of the intricate anatomy of human teeth is an essential prerequisite to all dental procedures especially in the case of root canal treatment. Anatomical relationship between the pulp and the periodontal structures plays a major role in the etiopathogenesis of the pulp or pulp periodontal lesions. Lateral canals may comprise of potential pathways through which bacteria or their products may reach the periodontal ligament and likewise. This, often overlooked aspect contribute to persistence of periapical lesion even after the completion of endodontic treatment. Therefore, this library dissertation attempts to present a comprehensive review on the origin, frequency, location and prevalence of lateral canals in primary and permanent dentition.

KEY WORDS: canal, etiopathogenesis, pulp, lateral, treatment

INTRODUCTION:

A clear understanding of the anatomy of human teeth is an essential prerequisite to all dental procedures especially so in the case of root canal treatment which deals with management of the tooth's internal anatomy. The pulp space is divided into two parts: Pulp chamber and Pulp canal or Root canal. The pulp space is complex; root canals may divide and rejoin and possess forms that are considerably more evolved than commonly implied.^[1]

The anatomical relationship between the pulp and the periodontal structures plays a major role in the etiopathogenesis of the pulp or pulp-periodontal lesions. Lateral canals comprise potential pathways through which bacteria or their products from the infected root canal might reach the periodontal ligament (PDL) and cause disease and likewise, bacteria from periodontal pockets might reach the pulp.^[2]

In general, while performing root canal therapy primary focus remains on the treatment of the

main canals and its bifurcations and lateral canals are often overlooked. Lateral canals exist in 9.3 to 19 percent of the population^[3]. Frequency of missed lateral canal is more than 35 percent constituting up to 12 percent of periapical pathology. Cantator *et al*^[4] observed that lateral canals are more common in multi-rooted teeth as compared to single rooted teeth.

While term lateral canal is often interchanged with accessory canal, all the branches of the major root canal or pulp chamber communicating with the periodontium are accessory canals however when these canals are situated in the middle or coronal third of the root and have a horizontal course extending perpendicular from the main root canal, these are termed as lateral canals.^[5]

This article would present a comprehensive update on the terminologies, classification and orientation of lateral canals with a deep insight into its incidence with respect to type of teeth, location, patient age etc with the aim of widening the clinician's perspective for better management of lateral canals.

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TERMINOLOGIES:

LATERAL CANAL:

Cheung *et al* (2007)^[6] defined a lateral canal as a branch which diverges almost at right angles from the main canal.

According to the AAE Glossary of Endodontic Terms (AAE 2016)^[7], a lateral canal is also a type

of accessory canal, located in the coronal or middle third of the root, usually extending horizontally from the main canal space, while a furcation canal is an accessory canal located in the furcation.

Çalışkanet al(1995)^[8] defined lateral canals as accessory canals located in the coronal, middle as well as apical third of the root.

ACCESSORY CANAL:

Cheung *et al* (2007)^[6] defined an accessory canal as a fine branch of the pulp canal that diverges at an oblique angle from the main canal to exit into the periodontal ligament space.

According to the AAE Glossary of Endodontic Terms (AAE 2016)^[7], an accessory canal is a branch of the main pulp canal or chamber that communicates with the external root surface.

Ahmed *et al* (2016)^[5] defined an accessory canal as a small canal leaving the root canal that usually communicates with the external surface of the root or furcation located anywhere along the length of the root (coronal, middle or apical third), and can be any type (patent, blind, loop).

It also includes what have been in the past termed lateral canals.

ACCESSORY APICAL FORAMINA and LATERAL CANAL FORAMINA:

Green (1955)^[9] considered foramina of accessory canals located within 3.5mm of apex as accessory apical foramina however if the number exceeded three he referred it as multiple foramina. Any accessory foramina present beyond 3.5 mm was termed as lateral canal foramina.

Cheung *et al* (2007)^[6] defined an auxiliary/accessory foramen as the exit of lateral or any accessory canal, or of an apical delta.

According to the AAE glossary of terms (AAE 2016)^[7], an accessory foramen is an orifice on the surface of the root communicating with a lateral or accessory canal.

Ahmed *et al* (2016)^[5] defined an accessory foramen as the opening of an accessory or a chamber canal on the external surface of the root or furcation. However, these accessory canals may be patent, blind or looped or may not necessarily terminate in accessory foramina.

DEVELOPMENT OF ACCESSORY CANALS:

Seltzer *et al* (1967)^[10] hypothesized that accessory canals are caused by a localized failure in the formation of Hertwig's Epithelial Root Sheath. This failure in Hertwig's Sheath results in lack of odontoblast differentiation and formation of dentin at this point leading to formation of accessory canal which connects the periodontal ligament with the pulp chamber. The authors were of the view that the gap in the Hertwig's sheath is likely produced by the persistence of abnormally placed blood vessels reaching the pulp. According to several studies using human teeth, a single or one pair of blood vessels existed in one accessory canal although the slit-like canals in the root apex regions might contain two or more blood vessels^[3].

CLASSIFICATION OF ACCESSORY CANALS:

Classification serves as a simple and accurate reflection of the complexity of accessory canal configuration and is necessary to give a detailed idea about the orientation and morphology of accessory canals.

Yoshiuchi *et al* (1972)^[11] classified lateral canals on the basis of their location with respect to the main canal. The length of root from cervical margin to apex was divided into tenths and categorization of accessory canals was as follows (Figure 1a):

- Ø 5/10 to 9/10 of the root length – Cervically located
- Ø 4/10 to 2/10 of the root length - Located in Middle
- Ø 1/10 or less of the root length – Apically Located

Yoshiuchiet al (1972)^[11] used hypothetical cross section of a root to define orientation of accessory canal: (Figure 1b)

- Ø 12 o'clock - centre of the buccal (labial) surface
- Ø 6 o'clock - centre of palatal (lingual) surface
- Ø 11 and 1 o'clock - buccal (labial) surface
- Ø 1 and 2 o'clock - mesio-labial, 2 and 4 o'clock - mesial and so on.

Vertucciet al (1974)^[12] classified lateral canals according to their location: (Figure 1c)

- Ø Coronal
- Ø Middle
- Ø Apical or furcation

De-Deus (1975)^[3] categorized accessory canal morphology into: (Figure 1d)

- a) Lateral canal extending from the main canal to the

1a: Classification of lateral canals based on their position along the root length (Yoshiuchi *et al*); 1b: Orientation of the accessory canals with the use of a hypothetical cross-section of a root with an accessory canal (Yoshiuchi *et al*); 1c: Classification of lateral canals according to their location along length of root (Vertucci *et al*); 1d: Classification of accessory canal morphology along root length (De-Deus).

periodontal ligament (In the body of the root).

- b) Secondary canal extending from the main canal to the periodontal ligament (In apical region).
- c) Accessory canal which is derived from the secondary canal branching off to the periodontal ligament in the apical region.

Accessory canal in furcation area have been classified by Yoshida *et al* (1975)^[13] and Paras *et al* (1993).^[14] (Figure 2a)

- a) Type 1 canals in which periodontium and pulpal chamber communicate through patent accessory canals.
- b) Type 2 - originating from the pulp chamber and ending in dentine.
- c) Type 3 - originating from the periodontium and ending in dentine.
- d) Type 4 - originating from the pulp chamber transverse through dentine, and return to the pulp chamber.
- e) Type 5 -originating from the periodontium transverse through dentine and cementum and returning to the periodontium.
- f) Type 6 – Present in dentine and/or cementum but with no exit.

Matsunaga *et al* (2014)^[15] modified Weine FS *et al* (1982)^[16] classification for root canal morphology and proposed a subclassification.

He divided Weines classification into four subtypes: (Figure 2b)

- a) No accessory root canals.
- b) With apical ramifications.
- c) With lateral canals.
- d) Both apical ramifications and lateral canals observed at the same time.

Kasahara *et al* 1990^[17] divided the root canal length into the sixth and proposed the following classification of lateral canals based on their position (Figure 2c).

The level of an accessory canal was classified as between:

- Ø 1/6 to 2/6 of the root length - Apically Located
- Ø 2/6 to 3/6 of the root length - Located in Middle
- Ø 3/6 to 4/6 of the root length - Cervically located

Kasahara *et al* (1990)^[17] classified Orientation of eccentrically located apical foramen as (Figure 2d):

- Ø Buccal, BuccoMesial, BuccoDistal, Lingual, LinguoMesial, LinguoDistal, Mesial, Distal.

Caliskan *et al* 1995^[18] found presence of one or more

2a: Classification of furcation canals(Yoshida *et al* and Paras *et al*); 2b: Classification of lateral canals(Matsunaga *et al*); 2c: Classification of lateral canals based on location along root (Kasahara *et al*); 2d: Classification of canals according to Orientation of eccentrically located apical foramen (Kasahara *et al*); 2e: Classification of lateral canals and lateral canal morphology(Ahmed *et al*).

lateral branching of the main canal along the root length and classified lateral canals on basis of their location as:

Ø Coronal, Middle, Apical, Coronal/Middle, Coronal/Apical, Middle/Apical, Coronal/Middle/ Apical thirds

Ahmed *et al* 2017^[5] gave a new system of classification in which they used the codes of root and root canal morphology allocated for single, double and multirooted teeth (Figure 2e).

The length of the root is divided into thirds (T): the coronal third (C), which starts from an imaginary line from the most apical portion of the pulp chamber, middle third (M) and apical third (A) ending at the root apex.

Each third is identified as a superscript within parenthesis after the tooth number [TN(T)], e.g. [TN(C), TN(M), TN(A)], or after the individual root s if the tooth is double/multi -rooted, e.g. [2TN R1(T) R2] (R: Root). If the accessory canal branches from a single canal coronal to a root bifurcation, then the superscript is written before the root notation, e.g. 2TN (T) R1 R2.

Accessory canal(s) should define the continuous course of the starting from the accessory-orifices (aO), through the canal (C) to the accessory -

foramen (foramina) (aF) – (aO - C - aF).

If the aO of an accessory canal is in one third of the root but the aF is located in another third, then a comma is added between the two regions of the root (e.g TN (M,AaO - C - aF)). An apical delta is identified by the letter “D”. The tooth type and code are respectively:

Tooth type	Code
Ø Single-rooted	- 1TNO-C-F
Ø Double-rooted	- 2TN R1O-C-F R2O-C-F
Ø Multirooted	- nTN R1O-C-F R2O-C-F RnO-C-F

*TN- tooth number, R – root, O – orifice, C – canal F- foramen, n - refers to three roots or more.

FREQUENCY AND LOCATION OF ACCESSORY CANALS:

Studies have proven the intimate relationship between pulp and periodontal tissue through which exchange of toxic products and inflammatory extensions may occur leading to pathological situations and resultant concomitant pulpal periodontal breakdown.

Root canal may communicate with periodontal ligament through the base, body, and the apex.^[11] Ricciet *al* (2010)^[19] observed that in maximum cases ramification were found in the apical third (73.5%) followed by coronal third(15%) and middle third(11%).

A study on 1,140 teeth carried out by Deus *et al* (1975)^[3] showed the presence of accessory canals in 313 teeth (27.4%) and they were most frequent in the apical area (17.0%), less frequent in the body of the root (8.8%), and least frequent in the base of the root (1.6%). The lateral canals were found in 10.4% of the total teeth studied. 2.3% of the bifurcation and trifurcation areas of the premolars and molars studied, demonstrated lateral canals that emanated from the main canal. No lateral canals originated from the pulp chamber.

In a study, Venturi M *et al* ^[20] 28.4% teeth exhibited patent accessory canals in the furcation region out of total 102 teeth (51 mandibular and 51 maxillary). In this area canals were noted in 29.4% of mandibular molars (21 canals) and 27.4% of maxillary molars (22 canals). In the "furcation" area 24.5% (30) teeth demonstrated patent accessory canals whereas lateral canals were noted in 25.5% of mandibular molars (14 canals) and 23.5% of maxillary molars (16 canals). 11.8% of the mandibular molars and 7.8% of the maxillary molars had accessory canals on lateral root surfaces.^[21]

Lowman *et al* (1973)^[22] reported presence of accessory canals in 59% of the teeth. There was significant difference observed in maxillary and mandibular teeth i.e. 55% of maxillary and 63% of mandibular teeth exhibited accessory canals. The incidence of accessory canals was significantly more in apical region as compared to middle and coronal third (Table 1).

PRESENCE OF ACCESSORY CANALS IN PRIMARY TEETH:

The incidence of accessory canals in primary molars varies greatly in the literature, with values ranging from 23% to 94% (Dammachke *et al*. 2004)^[23]. In a study by Berscheid *et al* (2012)^[24], 83% of primary molars were found to have at least one accessory canal and patent accessory canals were found to occur at an incidence of 8% in extracted primary molars scanned using micro-CT.

Moss *et al* (1965)^[25] and Wrbas *et al* (1997)^[26] on using histologic sectioning found the incidence of patent canals to be 20% and 30%, respectively. Moss *et al*^[25] stated that a majority of patent accessory canals entered the pulp chamber at the region of least thickness, where the floor of the pulp chamber slopes into the roots and the minority of patent accessory canals entered through the height of greatest curvature in the centre of the pulp chamber. Multiple accessory canals on the root close to the furcation were observed.

It has been reported by both Kramer *et al* (2003)^[27] and Paras *et al* (1993)^[14] that the vast majority of accessory canals are located on the outer surface of the furcation, attached to the periodontal ligament, and only a small minority are located on the inner surface of the furcation adjacent to the pulpal floor.

When observed using Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM), Paras *et al* ^[14] found that 20% of teeth had an accessory canal on the inner surface and 50% had canals on the outer surface of the furcation. Likewise, Kramer *et al* ^[27] also used SEM to find that 25% of teeth had a canal on the inner surface of the furcation while 53% had a canal on the outer surface of the furcation.

Study by Berscheid *et al* (2012)^[24], found that 11% of all teeth studied had a canal only on the inner surface of the furcation and 64% had a canal only on the outer surface of the furcation, 8% of teeth had patent canals and the remaining 17% had no canals (Table 2).

RELATIONSHIP OF INCIDENCE OF ACCESSORY CANALS IN MAXILLARY AND MANDIBULAR TEETH:

Previous studies comparing the incidence of accessory foramina in maxillary and mandibular first and second molars showed that while the prevalence of foramina in the different teeth surveyed was not equal, no statistically significant difference was observed and it could not be concluded that more foramina are located in maxillary versus mandibular teeth or first versus second molars.

Literature reveals that accessory canals appear equally in maxillary and mandibular teeth, and there was no significant difference between presence of accessory canals in first and second primary molars.^[28]

Morabito *et al* (1982)^[29] found no association between the presence of canals and the type of primary molar however a significant relationship was found between the number of canals observed in first and second molars. Second molars had a significantly higher number of canals as compared to first molars.

PATIENT AGE AND PRESENCE OF ACCESSORY CANALS:

Two contrasting opinions are present in literature regarding the patient age and presence of accessory canals.

Although Berscheid *et al*^[24] found no relation between patient age and presence of canals or the number however Woo *et al* ^[28] stated that there seemed to be an inverse relationship between the age of the patients and the prevalence of accessory canals in molars and also hypothesized that this trend could be

Table 1: Summary of Research of Accessory Canals in Permanent teeth.

Author	Tooth type and Sample size	Number and percentage of accessory canals	Location	Method to access Presence of Lateral canals.	Other findings
Pineda and kuttler (1972)	Maxillary and mandibular first molars (300)	0	Furcation	Radiography	
Lowman et al(1973)	Maxillary and mandibular first and second molars (46)	28 (60%)	Apical(20%) Middle(8%) Coronal(12%)	Contrast and radiography	Lesions that involve the furcation region of multirooted teeth may have an endodontic as well as a periodontal origin.
Vertucci and Williams (1974)	Maxillary and mandibular first molars (102)	43 (42%)	Maximum in apical region	Tooth clearing technique and dye penetration	
Dues et al (1975)	Premolar and molars (1140)	313 (27%)	Apical(17%) Middle(8.8%) Coronal(8.8%)	Tooth clearing technique with dye penetration	
Burch and Hulen (1974)	Maxillary and mandibular first and second molars (100)	76 (76%)	Maximum in apical region	Dye penetration	
Hession (1977)	Maxillary and mandibular first and second molars (13)	0 (0%)	Furcation region	Contrast radiography	
Gutmann (1978)	Maxillary and mandibular first and second molars (150)	46 (30%)	Maximum in apical region	Dye penetration	
Perlich <i>et al</i> (1981)	Maxillary and mandibular first and second molars (31)	22 (70%)	Maximum in apical region	Dye penetration and SEM	
Vertucci and Anthony (1986)	Maxillary and mandibular first molars (25)	7 (28%)	Furcation area	SEM	
Seow W et al(1989)	Maxillary and mandibular molars (102)	29 (28%)	Maximum in apical	Dye penetration	
Niemann <i>et al</i> (1993)	Maxillary and mandibular first molars (25)	12 (48%)	Furcation region	Dye penetration and surface visualization	
da Mata <i>et al</i> (2004)	Maxillary and mandibular first and second molars (140)	32 (22%)	N/A	SEM	
Silveira da Cunha <i>et al</i> (2005)	Maxillary and mandibular first and second molars (21)	16 (76.1%)	Cavo - interradicular	SEM	
Ricucci et al(2010)	All maxillary and mandibular teeth (493)	369 (74%)	Apical(73.5%) Middle(11%) Coronal(15%)	Extraction and histological examination.	The belief that lateral canals must be injected with filling material to enhance treatment outcome was not supported by literature review
Gerhard WT et al(2018)	Maxillary and mandibular molars (117)	18 (15%)	N/A	Dye penetration	

Table 2: Summary of Research of Accessory Canals in deciduous teeth²⁴

Author	Method	Sample Size (N)	% Teeth With Accessory Foramin	% Teeth With Patent Canals	Canal Diameter (µm)	Other Findings
Paras et al. (1993)	SEM	20	35	N/A	5-175	N/A
Kramer et al. (2003)	SEM	60	53 on EFA 25 on IFA	N/A	20-222	- No significance in presence of canals between healthy and necrotic pulps
Dammaschke et al. (2004)	SEM	100	94	N/A	10-360	- Significantly more foramin in primary molar furcation than permanent molar furcation
Luglie et al. (2012)	SEM	30	77	N/A	4-300	- All teeth examined extracted for orthodontic reasons
Winter et al. (1962)	Dye Penetration Under Vacuum Suction	100	23	N/A N/A		N/A
Woo et al. (1981)	Dye Penetration & Histologic Sectioning	157	32 (Dye Penetration) 25 (Histologic Sectioning)	N/A		- Inverse relation between patient age and prevalence of accessory canals. Higher prevalence in male patients
Wrbas et al. (1997)	Histologic Sectioning	40	77	30 N/A		- 17 % of orifices found on pulp chamber floor, 83% on interradicular aspect
Moss et al. (1965)	Histologic Sectioning	56	N/A	20 N/A		N/A
Paras et al. (1993)	Latex perfusion	25	N/A	4 N/A		N/A
Simpson (1973)	Silicone Perfusion	150	N/A	N/A N/A		N/A

explained by the obliteration of some of the canals with age. The authors found that with the increase in the patient age there was decrease in the incidence of accessory canals in molars. Hence, it can be concluded that although there might be no effect on the number (presence/absence) but status of lateral canals (patent/obliteration) might be affected.

Incidence of Accessory Foramina:

Not all the accessory canals terminate with an

opening on the outer surface of the root.

Though majority of accessory and lateral canals have exits on the outer root surface called as accessory or lateral foramina but some accessory canals terminate within the root without having any communication with the outer surface.

A morphologic study by Dammaschke T *et al* (2004)^[23] on 100 permanent molars revealed that 79% had presence of lateral/accessory foramina. Their diameters ranged from 10–200 micrometers. The

largest diameter was nearly two to three times smaller than the mean diameters reported for the main apical foramen.

The incidence of accessory foramina is reported to be higher in primary molars than in permanent molars with 94% of primary molars having accessory foramina with diameter ranging from 10u to 360u.^[30]

A stereomicroscopic study of 700 root apices of maxillary and mandibular posterior teeth found presence of accessory foramina in more than 70% of the teeth and average accessory foramina were about one-half the size of major foramina and twice the distance from the apex.^[31]

Paras *et al* (1993)^[14] on examination by Scanning Electron Microscopy found that 20% of the molars had presence of accessory foramina in internal furcation area and 50% of the molars on the external furcation surface demonstrated accessory foramina.

CONCLUSION:

Inappropriately managed lateral canals may serve as potential pathway for ingress of bacteria from necrotic root canal to PDL or vice versa.

A knowledge of prevalence, configuration and orientation of the lateral and accessory canals may help the clinicians in better management of these canals as to attain adequate cleaning and shaping with three dimensional seal.

REFERENCES:

- Vertucci F. Root canal anatomy of the human permanent teeth. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 1984;5(1):589-99.
- Ahmed H, Hashem A. Accessory roots and root canals in human anterior teeth: A review and clinical considerations. *J Endod.* 2016;4(1):724-36.
- Deus D. Frequency, location, and direction of the lateral, secondary, and accessory canals. *J Endod.* 1975;1(11):361-6.
- Cantator G, Berutti E, Castellucci A. Missed anatomy: Frequency and clinical impact. *J Endod.* 2006;15(1):3-31.
- Ahmed H, Versiani M, Deus D, Dummer P. A new system for classifying root and root canal morphology. *Int Endod J.* 2016;50(8):761-70.
- Cheung GS, Yang J, Fan B. Morphometric study of the apical anatomy of C-shaped root canal systems in mandibular second molars. *Int Endod. J* 2007; 4(1): 239-46.
- AAE – American Association of Endodontists. Glossary of terms. 2016.
- Caliskan MK, Pehlivan Y, Sepetcioglu F, Turkun M, Tuncer SS. Root canal morphology of human permanent teeth in a Turkish population. *J Endod.* 1995;2(1):200-4.
- Green D. A stereo-binocular microscopic study of the root apices and surrounding areas of 100 mandibular molars; Preliminary study. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 1955;8(1):1298-304.
- Seltzer S, Bender I, Nazimov H, Sinai I. Pulpitis-induced interradicular periodontal changes in experimental animals. *J Periodontol.* 1967;38(2):124-9.
- Yoshiuchi Y, Takahashi K, Yokochi C. Studies of the anatomical forms of the pulp cavities with new method of vacuum injection. (II) – Accessory canal and apical ramification. *Japanes J Oral Biol.* 1972;14(1):156-85.
- Vertucci M, Prati C, Capelli G, Falconi M, Breschi L. A preliminary analysis of the morphology of lateral canals after root canal filling using a tooth-clearing technique. *Int Endod J* 2003;36(1):54-63.
- Yoshida H, Yakushiji M, Sugihara A, Tanaka K, Taguchi M. Accessory canals at floor of the pulp chamber of primary molars. *J Can Dent Assoc.* 1975;75(1):580-5.
- Paras LG, Rapp R, Piesco NP, Zeichner SJ, Zullo TG. An investigation of accessory canals in furcation areas of human primary molars: Part 2. Latex perfusion studies of the internal and external furcation areas to demonstrate accessory canals. *J Clin Pediatr Dent.* 1993;17(2):71-7.
- Matsunaga S, Shimoo Y, Kinoshita H. Morphologic classification of root canals and incidence of accessory canals in maxillary first molar palatal roots: Three dimensional observation and measurements using micro-CT. *J Can Dent Assoc.* 2015;23(1):329-34.
- Weine FS. *Endodontic Therapy*, 3rd edn. St. Louis: Mosby;1982.
- Kasahara E, Yasuda E, Yamamoto A, Anzai M. Root canal system of the maxillary central incisor. *J Endod.* 1990;16(1):158-61.
- Caliskan MK, Pehlivan Y, Sepetcioglu F, Turkun M, Tuncer SS. Root canal morphology of human permanent teeth in a Turkish population. *J Endod.* 1995;21(1):200-4.
- Ricucci D, Arnold M, Siqueira JF. Infection in a complex network of apical ramifications as the cause of persistent apical periodontitis: A case report. *J Endod.* 2013;39(1):1179-84.
- Venturi M, Lenarda R, Prati C, Breschi L. An *in vitro* model to investigate filling of lateral canals. *J Endod.* 2005;3(1):877-81.
- Ringelstein D, Seow W. The prevalence of furcation foramina in primary molars. *J Clin Pediatr Dent.* 1989;11(3):198-202.
- Lowman V, Burke S, Pelleu B. Patent accessory canals: Incidence in molar furcation region. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 1973 Oct;36(4):580-4.
- Dammaschke T, Witt M, Ott K, Schafer E. Scanning electron microscopic investigation of incidence, location, and size of accessory foramina in primary and permanent molars. *Quintessence International.*

- 1985;35(9):699-705.
24. Berscheid M, Seelig A, Gillis R. Root canal morphology of the human maxillary second premolar. *Oral Surg Oral Med Oral Pathol.* 2012;38(1):456–64.
 25. Moss S, Addelston H, Goldsmith D. Histologic study of pulpal floor of deciduous molars. *J Am Dent Assoc.* 1965;70(1):372-9.
 26. Wrbas K, Kielbassa M, Hellwig E. Microscopic studies of accessory canals in primary molar furcations. *ASDC J Dent Child.* 1997;64(2):118-22.
 27. Kramer P, Faraco J, Meira, R. A SEM investigation of accessory foramina in the furcation areas of primary molars. *J Clin Pediatr Dent.* 2003;27(2):157-61.
 28. Woo R, Miller J. Accessory canals in deciduous molars. *J Clin Pediatr Dent* 1981;12(2):51-7.
 29. Morabito A, Defabianis P. A SEM investigation on pulpal-periodontal connections in primary teeth. *ASDC J Dent Child.* 1992;59(1):53-7.
 30. Soviero V, Leal C, Silva R, Azevedo B. Validity of MicroCT for *in vitro* detection of proximal carious lesions in primary molars. *J Endod.* 2012;40(1):35-40.
 31. Simpson W. An examination of root canal anatomy of primary teeth. *J Dent Educ.* 1973;39(9):637-40.

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